

EHMA 2025: Advancing demand-driven innovation adoption in paediatrics through the theory of change: insights from the ADD4kids project working groups

<p><i>When citing, sharing, or adapting this work, please provide proper attribution as follows:</i></p>	<p>Anael Barberan-Garcia, Olman Elizondo, Rossana Alessandrello, Ramon Maspons.</p> <p>Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of Catalonia (AQuAS), Spain.</p>
<p>Abstract</p>	<p>The ADD4kids project addresses the adoption of Demand-Driven Innovation (DDI) in paediatric healthcare, aiming to improve service delivery through a structured European framework for mainstreaming innovation procurement. Despite the potential of value-based procurement to enhance healthcare outcomes, its implementation faces significant barriers, including regulatory fragmentation, limited awareness, and institutional risk aversion. In paediatrics, these challenges are intensified by a small market size, inadequate reimbursement mechanisms, and limited procurement strategies. A lack of European consensus further constrains systematic adoption.</p> <p>Methods: The study applies the Theory of Change (ToC) framework to structure WP2 activities into inputs, activities, and staged outcomes (short-, mid-, and long-term).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Long-term outcome (2027): Sustainable improvement of paediatric healthcare through DDI mainstreaming. ● Mid-term outcome (2026): Identification and prioritisation of cross-border barriers and solutions for DDI adoption. ● Short-term outcomes (2025): Publication of a white paper on paediatric DDI strategies and development of an EU action plan for sustainable innovation adoption. <p>In 2024, nine online working groups were established under WP2, focusing on key barriers such as governance, funding, procurement, data integration, and clinical engagement. These groups used mixed qualitative methods including SWOT analysis, root cause analysis, surveys, and iterative collaborative workshops. Inputs included European Commission funding, WP1 desk research, and expert interviews.</p> <p>Results: Findings were synthesised into five main thematic areas:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Governance and Policy Alignment Key issues include regulatory fragmentation, weak coordination, and low policy prioritisation. Proposed solutions include establishing an EU paediatric procurement governance hub and harmonising regulatory frameworks. 2. Funding and Sustainability Challenges include short-term funding cycles and limited private investment. Recommended actions involve public-private funding models, financial incentives, and venture capital engagement. 3. Data and Digital Health Integration Barriers include fragmented datasets, legal constraints, and limited AI integration. Solutions focus on standardisation of paediatric data, GDPR-compliant data sharing, and AI-driven analytics. 4. Procurement and Market Engagement Constraints include small market size, complex procurement processes, and fragmented demand. Proposed interventions include joint procurement mechanisms, simplified procurement procedures, and capacity-building. 5. Clinical and Patient-Centred Innovation Issues include low clinician engagement and insufficient patient involvement. Solutions include institutionalised innovation time, patient advisory structures, and promotion of risk-tolerant innovation cultures. <p>Discussion: The study highlights that fragmentation across governance, funding, data systems, and procurement significantly impedes DDI adoption in paediatrics. Financial sustainability remains fragile due to dependence on short-term funding mechanisms. Data standardisation and interoperability are critical enablers for regulatory and operational progress. Misalignment among stakeholders slows implementation, while procurement complexity remains a structural barrier. The Theory of Change provides a coherent framework to align interventions with desired outcomes, supporting the development of a coordinated EU-wide roadmap for paediatric innovation adoption.</p>

Advancing demand-driven innovation adoption in paediatrics through the theory of change: insights from the ADD4kids project working groups (ID 329)

Dr Anael Barberan-Garcia, Olman Elizondo, Rossana Alessandrello, Ramon Maspons
Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of Catalonia (AQuAS), Spain

Context: Demand-driven innovation (DDI) adoption is crucial for improving healthcare delivery, yet value-based procurement faces challenges such as regulatory barriers, lack of awareness, and risk aversion. Paediatrics encounters additional hurdles, including inadequate reimbursement, limited procurement strategies, and a restricted market. Despite various initiatives, a European consensus on paediatric DDI adoption is lacking. This abstract presents findings from nine working groups nested in the work package (WP) 2 of the ADD4kids project. The main objective of WP2 is to develop a framework to mainstream DDI instruments for paediatrics. ADD4kids aims to create a structured roadmap for mainstreaming paediatric DDI adoption.

Methods: We applied the Theory of Change (ToC) to define the strategic vision of WP2, structured into Inputs, Activities, and Short, Mid, and Long-Term Outcomes. The Long-Term Outcome (2027) aligns with ADD4kids' mission: enhancing paediatric healthcare. The Mid-Term Outcome (2026) is to identify, prioritize and address cross-border challenges through DDI adoption. Short-Term Outcomes (2025) include: (i) publishing a white paper on strategies to enhance DDI adoption in paediatrics and (ii) developing an EU action plan for sustainable paediatric innovation adoption. In 2024, WP2's main Activities involved nine online working groups tackling key DDI adoption challenges, including internal alignment, upskilling, policy and funding, cross-border procurement, and health system interventions. Using collaborative tools, these groups conducted SWOT and root cause analyses, brainstorming sessions, and surveys, refining insights iteratively. Inputs (2024) included European Commission funding, along with a WP1-derived desk review on DDI and structured expert interviews.

Results: The working groups' findings represent the Short-Term Outcomes identified through the ToC. Below, the summarized insights categorized into five key themes:

1. Governance and Policy Alignment

- Challenges: Lack of coordination, regulatory discrepancies, low policy prioritization.
- Solutions: Establish an EU Paediatric Procurement Governance Hub, harmonize regulations, strengthen advocacy

2. Funding and Sustainability

- Challenges: Reliance on short-term funding, low private sector investment, insufficient hospital incentives.
- Solutions: Implement long-term public-private funding, develop financial incentives, attract venture capital

3. Data and Digital Health Integration

- Challenges: Fragmented data, legal constraints, lack of AI integration.
- Solutions: Standardize paediatric data, enable GDPR-compliant sharing, integrate AI-driven analytics.

4. Procurement and Market Engagement

- Challenges: Small market size, complex procurement, fragmented demand.
- Solutions: Develop joint procurement alliances, simplify processes, enhance procurement training.

5. Clinical and Patient-Centred Innovation

- Challenges: Limited clinician participation, overlooked patient perspectives, institutional barriers.
- Solutions: Institutionalize "Innovation Time," create patient advisory boards, foster risk-tolerance culture.

Discussion: This study identified key challenges of paediatric DDI adoption and its potential solutions. Key takeaways include:

- DDI efforts fragmentation hinders paediatric innovation highlighting the need for strong cross-border governance
- Financial sustainability remains a challenge due to reliance on short-term EU funding.
- Data sharing and standardization play a crucial role in regulatory approval and adoption.
- Stakeholder misalignment slows progress, requiring structured engagement strategies.
- Procurement complexities hinder DDI adoption, necessitating targeted solutions.

The ToC provides a structured framework to align activities with outcomes, laying the groundwork for a collaborative and comprehensive EU action plan for paediatric DDI adoption.